

Decoding Knowledge Claims: The Evaluation of Scientific Publication Contributions through Semantic Analysis

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The surge in scientific publications challenges the use of publication counts as a measure of scientific progress, requiring alternative metrics that emphasize the quality and novelty of scientific contributions rather than sheer quantity. This paper proposes the use of Relaxed Word Mover’s Distance (RWMD), a semantic text similarity measure, to evaluate the novelty of scientific papers. We hypothesize that RWMD can more effectively gauge the growth of scientific knowledge. To test such an assumption, we apply RWMD to evaluate seminal papers, with Hirsch’s H-Index paper as a primary case study. We compare RWMD results across three groups: 1) H-Index-related papers, 2) scientometric studies, and 3) unrelated papers, aiming to discern redundant literature and hype from genuine innovations. Findings suggest that emphasizing knowledge claims offers a deeper insight into scientific contributions, marking RWMD as a promising alternative method to traditional citation metrics, thus better tracking significant scientific breakthroughs.

1. Introduction

The growth of scientific knowledge has traditionally been measured by the volume of publications (Price, 1963). This metric has been the primary gauge of productivity and impact in academia for decades. This quantitative approach has long been used to evaluate academic progress and allocate research funding. However, the reliability of publication counts as a metric of scientific advancement is becoming increasingly questioned (Chen, 2012). In recent years, the academic world has been inundated by an unprecedented number of published papers (Nane et al., 2023). This phenomenon has led to concerns about literature saturation and the genuine contribution of many works (Landhuis, 2016). This growth in publication volume has raised significant doubts about the validity and value of contributions, leading to what can be described as an information overproduction (Arnold et al., 2023). In response to these challenges, there is a growing consensus on the need for alternative metrics that can more accurately identify true innovation and contributions of papers (Shibayama and Wang, 2019). Several approaches were proposed for redefining how scientific knowledge is measured (Wang, 2016; Azoulay et al., 2011; Foster et al., 2015; Shibayama & Wang, 2019). These methodologies focus on the analysis of knowledge claims, which are defined as novel and original contributions to the current state-of-the-art within specific fields (Shibayama and Wang, 2019). Still, they are all based on citation and publication metrics. Accordingly, Natural

Language Processing (NLP) techniques can help to identify knowledge claims, representing granular, qualitative approaches to assessing the content of scientific publications, focusing on the substantive quality and novelty of the research rather than merely its presence in the literature.

This paper proposes an innovative NLP approach to evaluating these knowledge claims. By shifting the focus from sheer output to the quality of contributions, this method aims to provide a more nuanced understanding of scientific growth, reducing the emphasis on publication quantity as the sole indicator of scientific progress. By applying semantic statistical analysis, we aim to explore the textual similarities and differences within scientific papers, thereby identifying redundancies, hype, and disruptive innovations pushing the boundaries of knowledge.

2. Methodology

Developing effective text similarity measurement techniques is central to numerous applications in NLP. Traditional approaches often rely on measuring the overlap of terms between documents. These methods, such as Bag-of-Words and TF-IDF, focus on quantifying the direct textual overlap without considering the semantic relationships between words that appear in different texts (Qader et al., 2019; Dumais et al., 1988; Blej et al., 2003). Such approaches are intuitive and straightforward but fall short of capturing the nuanced semantic similarities that might exist between texts with little to no direct term overlap. This is a significant drawback in many real-world scenarios where language's context and semantic richness play a crucial role in understanding the similarity between documents. To address the semantic gap, the field of NLP has turned towards word embeddings. Word embeddings represent words in a high-dimensional space as vectors. These vectors capture semantic properties such that semantically similar words are located in proximity within this space. Models like Word2Vec, GloVe, and FastText are popular examples of word embedding (Mikolov et al., 2013a; Mikolov et al., 2013b; Pennington et al., 2014).

An innovative approach that leverages the power of word embeddings to measure text similarity is the Word Mover's Distance (WMD), introduced by Kusner et al. (2015). Based on the classic Earth Mover's Distance (EMD), WMD calculates the minimum cumulative distance for words from one document to match the word distribution of another document exactly in the embedding space. The goal is to compute the minimum cost of transforming one document representation into another, using the distance between embeddings as the cost of word transformation. This method effectively captures texts' semantic differences and similarities, even if they have no words in common. While effective, the computational demands of WMD pose challenges when applied to large documents or those with a high number of unique words. The computational cost arises from solving the transportation problem, which is notably high, requiring super cubic time (Atasu et al., 2017; Wu et al., 2018). To mitigate this, the Relaxed Word Mover's Distance (RWMD) was proposed (Atasu, 2017), simplifying the optimization problem of WMD and making it more computationally efficient while leveraging the semantic richness of word embeddings. This is achieved by relaxing a constraint in the original WMD formulation, which reduces the computational complexity from super-cubic to linear time, depending on the implementation. As a result, RWMD allows for the rapid computation of semantic text similarity across large datasets, making it a practical choice for real-world applications where speed and scalability are crucial. Moreover, RWMD, given its simplicity and speed, emerges as one of the most successful outcomes of this research endeavour. In literature, some studies demonstrate its competitive quality compared to WMD, with the added benefit of significantly faster processing, especially for extensive vocabulary (Atasu et al., 2017; Werner & Laber, 2019).

3. Case study

To assess the effectiveness of RWMD in identifying knowledge redundancies or claims in scientific papers, we focus on the seminal paper by Hirsch (2005) that introduced the H-Index. This metric has been widely discussed and critiqued within the academic community. The H-Index's rapid adoption and extensive application resemble hype rather than a reflection of substantial intellectual advancement (Rousseau et al., 2013). To investigate these claims, we employ the RWMD to analyze the semantic similarity between Hirsch's paper and other scientific papers across different categories. In particular, we manually extract the text of the conclusion sections of papers, which summarize the authors' contributions, ideas, and proposals. However, the Hirsch document lacked distinct sections. Therefore, two selectors (LDA and MA) identified sentences containing the manuscript's proposal and novelty. Then, we measured the similarity distance of the H-Index document's proposal with the text conclusion of three distinct document groups:

- ***H-Index papers***: Papers that discuss or analyze the H-Index, derived from the review by Alonso et al. (2009). The comparison between Hirsch's original H-Index paper and subsequent papers that focus specifically on the H-Index allows for a direct evaluation of the influence and evolution of the H-Index within its domain. This group is crucial for understanding how Hirsch's ideas have been expanded upon, critiqued, or reinforced. By analyzing these papers, we can assess the degree of intellectual engagement with the H-Index concept and identify whether it has fostered incremental innovations or repeated the original ideas without significant additions.
- ***Scientometrics papers***: random papers published on scientometrics that do not focus on the H-Index. This comparison aims to highlight thematic divergences or convergences within the field that may not be directly influenced by the H-Index. The papers were retrieved from Scopus by searching all publications in the Scientometrics journal without any reference to the H-index or Hirsch.
- ***Random papers***: A randomly selected set of papers from various disciplines to gauge the H-Index paper's influence or mention outside its immediate field, helping identify any interdisciplinary impact or lack thereof.

These groups were selected with the expectation of computing RWMD scores, which will likely vary significantly, reflecting the contextual usage of the H-Index across disciplines. Some fields may show unexpectedly lower scores due to adopting the H-Index as a performance metric, while others may show no significant semantic closeness, indicating limited or no influence. By clearly delineating these groups and articulating the specific expectations of each, the study enhances the robustness of its methodological approach.

The RWMD was employed to measure the semantic similarity between the Hirsch paper, labelled as the query document, and the papers in each group. A total of 32 papers related to the H-Index were retrieved from Alonso et al.'s review (2009). Subsequently, 32 papers were collected for the Scientometrics and Random groups to match this number. The word embedding used for the RWMD was GloVe (Pennington et al., 2014), an unsupervised model for word vector representation. GloVe is a count-based model that learns word vectors from their co-occurrence information, determining how frequently words appear together in large text corpora. It is a fast word embedding technique trained on word-word co-occurrence probabilities, capable of capturing semantic meanings that can be expressed as vector differences (Mohammed et al., 2020). Before employing the RWMD, the texts were preprocessed, tokenized, and normalized, converting all uppercase letters to lowercase, removing extra spaces, punctuation, and stopwords. Following preprocessing, the GloVe model embedding was employed, assigning a vector to each word of the texts and representing them

in an embedding vector space. Proximity in this space indicates similarity between words. Cosine similarity was used to measure the distance between word vectors, quantifying the cosine of the angle between them, with values ranging from 0 to 1. A cosine similarity of 1 signifies identical words, while 0 indicates no similarity.

Finally, we computed the RWMD between the query document (Hirsch's H-Index paper) and the documents from three groups. For each document, RWMD was measured relative to the query document, obtaining a value between 0 and 1, where 0 represents complete dissimilarity and 1 signifies semantic identical texts. The Kruskal-Wallis test was performed among the distance values of the three groups. Subsequently, pairwise comparisons were conducted using the Wilcoxon rank sum exact test to determine the statistical significance of differences between distances among pairs of groups.

By employing the semantic, statistical-based approach mentioned above, the distance of H-index groups from the query document is expected to be smaller than that of the Scientometrics and Random groups. This result would support the hypothesis and highlight a potential hype surrounding the topic, which may incentivize publications related to it. All analyses were conducted in R (v. 4.3.1). The RWMD distance and the GloVe model were computed using the *text2vec* package. Data, including the extracted texts from all selected articles, is freely available at the following link: <https://zenodo.org/records/10997154>.

4. Findings

The results of the RWMD are presented in Table 1, where the semantic similarity distance between each paper in the groups and the query document was measured. For each group, the median distance values and interquartile ranges are reported. Our findings confirm our hypothesis, demonstrating that the H-Index papers show a higher level of similarity with the query document (median = 0.5763) compared to papers in the second and third groups (medians = 0.4331 and 0.3466, respectively). Additionally, the similarity distances among groups were statistically significant, and pairwise comparisons using the Wilcoxon rank sum exact test also yielded statistical significance across all pairs of groups.

Using RWMD, we effectively assessed the text similarity concerning the Hirsch documents. Specifically, focusing on the H-Index papers, RWMD successfully identified related papers with minimal or broader contributions. For instance, the top three documents include a study on the introduction of the h(2)-index as an alternative to the h-index for evaluating scientific output (document 7), a paper on the use of the g-index to enhance the h-index for assessing scientific impact (document 1), and a study on the introduction of three refinements of the h_I -index (h_I^+ , h_I^* , h_I^A), as well as two refined h-indices (h^x and h^*) (document 10). The RWMD findings not only aid in detecting papers with similar or minimal contributions but also in identifying papers proposing entirely novel or different concepts compared to the query document. This may signify introducing new knowledge or topics unrelated to the research area. Such papers are ranked lowest in our findings, with a low similarity distance. Specifically, focusing on the last two documents, document 24 is the only paper in the groups discussing the widespread use of the H-index for evaluating individual scientists while highlighting its biases and limitations. On the other hand, document 23 delves into using citation data to assess scientific authors, raising questions about selected indicators' reliability and effectiveness in distinguishing between authors.

In the Scientometrics group, the top three similar documents identified by the RWMD are a study related to interdisciplinary research spanning from 1975 to 2005 across six domains, utilizing established indicators and a new Diversity Index (document 6); research on the assessment of four topic modeling algorithms using a test dataset from seven scientific fields, comparing different algorithms and indices (document 15); and the description of indexes measuring collaborative strength in a discipline (document 28). Conversely, the last two

documents focus on measures to quantify academic bibliographic database sizes, criticizing Google Scholar (document 8) and the use of word embedding in the mathematics research domain (document 25). Although all papers in this group are not related to the H-Index topic, it is interesting how the RWMD effectively captured semantic similarities, particularly evident in the contribution summarized in the text of the top three documents regarding the proposal of indexes.

Finally, the Random Papers group shows the lowest similarity distance about the query document. Indeed, their contributions are entirely unrelated to the Hirsch proposal. For instance, the first document is a survey that evaluates current fake news research by defining and differentiating it from related concepts, detailing interdisciplinary research, and reviewing detection methods from multiple perspectives (document 7). Meanwhile, the last two documents focus on AI applications in the water domain and a medical study about cell segregation (documents 28 and 31, respectively).

Table 1. RWMD similarity distances between each document and the query document are presented. Median values and interquartile ranges are reported for each group.

<i>H-Index papers</i>	<i>Scientometrics papers</i>	<i>Random papers</i>
Doc ID - Distance	Doc ID - Distance	Doc ID - Distance
7 - 0.7636	6 - 0.5435	7 - 0.5354
1 - 0.6729	15 - 0.5416	13 - 0.4784
10 - 0.6701	28 - 0.5367	21 - 0.4453
32 - 0.6680	1 - 0.5070	11 - 0.4329
2 - 0.6658	11 - 0.5030	2 - 0.4314
31 - 0.6583	31 - 0.4897	12 - 0.4261
20 - 0.6536	17 - 0.4881	8 - 0.4160
19 - 0.6276	20 - 0.4764	19 - 0.3992
11 - 0.6132	5 - 0.4760	18 - 0.3990
13 - 0.6130	2 - 0.4665	20 - 0.3837
8 - 0.6093	23 - 0.4654	25 - 0.3830
5 - 0.6065	27 - 0.4599	10 - 0.3798
14 - 0.5973	30 - 0.4479	24 - 0.3646
22 - 0.5935	22 - 0.4444	15 - 0.3594
3 - 0.5902	10 - 0.4443	3 - 0.3530
15 - 0.5788	13 - 0.4379	5 - 0.3487
9 - 0.5738	3 - 0.4283	23 - 0.3446
4 - 0.5678	29 - 0.4194	16 - 0.3277
28 - 0.5630	18 - 0.4174	9 - 0.3192
16 - 0.5575	9 - 0.4165	6 - 0.3172
17 - 0.5375	19 - 0.4100	32 - 0.3071
29 - 0.5372	14 - 0.4031	26 - 0.2973
25 - 0.5344	4 - 0.3977	30 - 0.2958
12 - 0.5210	12 - 0.3909	14 - 0.2893
18 - 0.5200	7 - 0.3904	1 - 0.2835
26 - 0.5138	32 - 0.3890	17 - 0.2821

	21 - 0.5121	24 - 0.3811	29 - 0.2695
	27 - 0.5053	16 - 0.3802	4 - 0.2573
	6 - 0.4886	26 - 0.3628	27 - 0.2494
	30 - 0.4652	21 - 0.3498	22 - 0.2481
	24 - 0.4555	8 - 0.3230	28 - 0.2210
	23 - 0.4265	25 - 0.3165	31 - 0.1862
Median	0.5763	0.4331	0.3466
[IQR]	[0.5208-0.6131]	[0.3908-0.4689]	[0.2878-0.3875]

Table 2. The distances among the three groups were compared using the Kruskal-Wallis test and pairwise comparisons using the Wilcoxon rank sum exact test.

*Significant $0.01 < p \leq 0.05$, **Significant $p \leq 0.01$

	p-value
Kruskall-Wallis test	<0.001**
Pairwise comparisons using Wilcoxon rank sum exact test	
H-Index papers vs Scientometrics papers	<0.001**
H-Index vs Random papers	<0.001**
Scientometrics papers vs Random papers	<0.001**

5. Conclusion and further developments

This study demonstrates the utility of employing the RWMD to evaluate the semantic similarity of scientific papers within and across different domains. Focusing on the seminal Hirsch H-Index paper as a query document, our analysis has provided a structured approach to measuring the intellectual proximity and thematic relevance of subsequent publications within scientometrics and beyond.

Our findings confirm that the H-Index papers, as expected, show a higher level of similarity with the Hirsch paper. This affirms the prevalent influence of the H-Index in discussions surrounding academic impact metrics. This underscores a saturation within the domain, where many papers reiterate or slightly modify existing concepts rather than propose groundbreaking new ideas. The significant similarity scores within this group point to a possible overemphasis on incremental advancements rather than substantial scholarly contributions.

Conversely, the analysis of papers from unrelated fields and other areas of scientometrics using RWMD effectively highlighted a broader range of thematic engagements. Specifically, the lower similarity scores for these papers indicate more diverse and varied contributions, suggesting that they engage with different topics and concepts compared to the H-Index proposals. Through this analysis, our contribution lies in illustrating how focusing on knowledge claims rather than sheer publication output can provide a more nuanced understanding of scientific growth. Measuring a semantic similarity distance among scientific documents could help identify redundant literature, hypes, and potentially disruptive innovations, offering a fresh perspective on evaluating scientific contributions. We propose an alternative approach to addressing the challenges of the publications' overproduction. It helps recognize areas saturated with repetitive literature and uncover novel ideas that could lead to significant shifts in research paradigms.

As the scientific community continues to expand, accompanied by rapid and uncontrolled growth of publications, the methodologies presented in this study could represent a foundational tool for future research assessments, encouraging a shift towards more meaningful and

impactful scientific inquiry. Although it has valuable insights, this study has some limitations. Future research should focus on integrating more diverse semantic analysis tools and embedding models to create a more dynamic and comprehensive framework for assessing scientific literature. The current study was limited to a comparative analysis among several documents. Expanding the dataset would allow a more thorough understanding of the semantic landscape across different scientific domains. In addition, this study used the GloVe to generate word embeddings. A comparison among different embedding models like Word2Vec, SciBERT, and BERT could be used to assess our proposal.

Open science practices

This study embraces open science practices, reflecting our commitment to transparency and accessibility in research. Data are freely available at the following link <https://zenodo.org/records/10997154>, ensuring that interested parties can access and verify our findings. The analysis using R, an open-access software, aligns with our dedication to utilizing tools that promote collaboration and reproducibility in scientific research.

Author contributions

Massimo Aria, Nicolás-Robinson García, Luca D’Aniello, Corrado Cuccurullo: Conceptualization; **Massimo Aria, Nicolás-Robinson García, Luca D’Aniello** Methodology; **Luca D’Aniello:** Data curation, Writing- Original draft preparation; **Massimo Aria, Nicolás-Robinson García:** Supervision; **Massimo Aria, Nicolás-Robinson García, Luca D’Aniello, Corrado Cuccurullo:** Writing- Reviewing and Editing

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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